

Amperometric Estimation of Nickel and Cobalt with 1,2,3-Benzotriazole

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1,2,3-Benzotriazole has been employed as a reagent for the amperometric titrations of nickel(II) and cobalt (II) in very dilute solutions. Nickel is titrated in presence of appropriate concentrations of ammonia and ammonium acetate as the supporting electrolytes (pH 7.2) and cobalt in ammonia-ammonium chloride medium at about same pH. Titrations are not in any way hampered by the presence of different amounts of foreign metal ions like calcium, magnesium, aluminium, iron(III), chromium(III) and lead.

THE use of 1,2,3-benzotriazole in the amperometric estimation of palladium has been described by Wilson and Wilson¹. In a previous communication² we have described the amperometric estimation of copper(II) with this reagent. Since this reagent also acts as good precipitants for nickel^{3,4} and cobalt^{3,4} at pH 7.0-8.5 suitable methods have been developed to titrate these two metal ions in solution amperometrically with this reagent.

It has been found that both these titrations are best carried out at pH 7.2 using a supporting electrolyte medium of 0.0005 molar ammonia and 0.05 molar ammonium acetate in case of nickel and 0.0005 molar ammonia and 0.05 molar ammonium chloride in case of cobalt. Under these conditions 1:1 metal-ligand compounds are formed as is the case with both palladium¹ and copper².

The applied voltages during titrations of nickel and cobalt were maintained at -1.4 volts (vs S.C.E.) and -1.6 volts (vs S.C.E.) respectively due to the fact that at these voltages nickel and cobalt ions got reduced developing high diffusion current while benzotriazole remained unaffected (Figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1.

M—Polarogram of 1 millimolar nickel solution in ammonia-ammonium acetate supporting electrolytes.
R—Polarogram of 1 millimolar 1,2,3-benzotriazole solution in ammonia-ammonium acetate supporting electrolytes

Dilute solutions of nickel and cobalt containing 0.28 millimolar to 4.54 millimolar concentrations of nickel and 0.28 millimolar to 4.52 millimolar concentrations of cobalt were thus titrated successfully using a

Fig. 2.

M—Polarogram of 1 millimolar cobalt solution in ammonia-ammonium chloride supporting electrolytes.
R—Polarogram of 1 millimolar 1,2,3-benzotriazole solution in ammonia-ammonium chloride supporting electrolytes.

simple manual polarographic set up. 0.005% gelatin was used as maximum suppressor in all these titrations. Both nickel and cobalt titrations were carried out in presence of different amounts of metal ions like calcium, magnesium, aluminium, iron(III), chromium(III) and lead with uniformly good results. Nickel and cobalt could not, however, be estimated in presence of each other by this procedure.

Experimental

Apparatus:

The polarographic set used to carry out these titrations and to record the polarograms has already been described⁵.

Reagents and Solutions :

1,2,3-Benzotriazole was prepared and purified according to the method already described².

For both nickel and cobalt titrations, 0.05 molar and 0.0125 molar benzotriazole solutions in 1 : 4 aqueous ethanol were used.

Nickel(II) solution : This was prepared by dissolving calculated amount of reagent grade nickel sulphate in definite volume of distilled water. The nickel content of the solution was accurately determined as nickel dimethylglyoxime.

Cobalt(II) solution : It was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of reagent grade cobalt chloride crystals in 500 ml distilled water. The cobalt content of this solution was estimated gravimetrically as cobalt sulphate.

Supporting Electrolyte solution for nickel titrations :

Ammonium acetate (77 g) and concentrated ammonia, 27% (0.7 ml) were mixed and dissolved in water and the volume of this mixture made up to 1000 ml and the resulting solution stored in well-stoppered bottle.

Supporting Electrolyte solution for cobalt titrations :

A.R. grade ammonium chloride (53.50 g) and concentrated ammonia (0.7 ml) were dissolved in water and the volume made up to 1000 ml. This solution was stored in well-stoppered bottle.

Other chemicals and reagents used were all of A.R. or G.R. quality.

Titration Procedure :

For the titrations, a number of solutions containing calculated amounts of nickel or cobalt, the supporting electrolyte solutions and the gelatin solution were prepared. Each of these nickel solutions thus prepared contained 0.0005 molar ammonia + 0.05 molar ammonium acetate as supporting electrolytes together with 0.005% gelatin as the maximum suppressor (pH 7.2) while those of the cobalt, the solutions contained 0.0005 molar ammonia + 0.05 molar ammonium chloride as the supporting electrolytes with 0.005% gelatin as the maximum suppressor (pH 7.2).

Titration of these solutions were then carried out at room temperature (30°) at an applied voltage of -1.4 volts (vs S.C.E.) in case of nickel and -1.6 volts (vs S.C.E.) in case of cobalt following the usual procedure.

The end points were determined from the points of intersection of the L-shaped curves (Figs 3 and 4) which resulted in all the cases.

Solutions containing 0.5 mg to 1 mg nickel or cobalt were titrated with 0.0125 molar benzotriazole solution while those containing 2 mg to 8 mg nickel or cobalt were titrated with 0.05 molar benzotriazole solution. Titration results are quite satisfactory with practically no error. Data in Tables 1 and 2 show that under the experimental conditions, 1 : 1 metal-ligand species are formed.

Fig. 3.

Amperometric titration curve of nickel solution with 1,2,3-benzotriazole.

Concentration of nickel solution = 0.00284 molar
 Concentration of the benzotriazole solution (reagent) = 0.0125 M
 V = initial volume of the nickel solution titrated
 v = volume of the benzotriazole solution added.

Fig. 4.

Amperometric titration curve of cobalt solution with 1,2,3-benzotriazole.

Concentration of cobalt solution = 0.01131 molar
 Concentration of the benzotriazole solution (reagent) = 0.05 molar
 V = initial volume of the cobalt solution titrated
 v = volume of the benzotriazole solution added.

Titration in presence of diverse metal ions :

Both nickel and cobalt titrations were carried out in presence of different quantities of a number of metal ions like Ca(II), Mg(II), Al(III), Fe(III), Cr(III) and Pb(II) without any interference.

Under the conditions of experiments, calcium and magnesium ions remained in solution while Fe(II), Al(III), Cr(III) and Pb(II) were precipitated out

TABLE 1. AMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF NICKEL WITH 1,2,3-BENZOTRIAZOLE

Nickel present millimoles $\times 10^2$	1,2,3-Benzotriazole consumed millimoles $\times 10^2$	Mole ratio Nickel/reagent
13.63	13.60	1 : 0.99
10.22	10.18	1 : 0.99
8.519	8.502	1 : 0.99
6.816	6.800	1 : 0.99
3.407	3.400	1 : 0.99
1.704	1.700	1 : 0.99
0.8519	0.8502	1 : 0.99

TABLE 2. AMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF COBALT WITH 1,2,3-BENZOTRIAZOLE

Cobalt present millimoles $\times 10^2$	1,2,3-Benzotriazole consumed millimoles $\times 10^2$	Mole ratio Cobalt reagent
13.57	13.60	1 : 1.00
10.18	10.22	1 : 1.00
8.484	8.502	1 : 1.00
6.787	6.800	1 : 1.00
3.393	3.400	1 : 1.00
1.696	1.700	1 : 1.00
0.8484	0.8502	1 : 1.00

before the titrations. Experiments carried out with varying amounts of nickel and cobalt (2-8 mg) having upto 100-fold excess of calcium and magnesium and ten-fold excess of Fe(III), Al(III), Cr(III) and Pb(II) showed that these amounts of the diverse ions did not interfere with the estimations of nickel and cobalt.

References

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